

ROLE OF AGRARIAN DISTRESS IN POVERTY DISPARITIES BETWEEN ST AND NON-ST IN RURAL INDIA: PANEL ANALYSIS WITH STATE LEVEL INFORMATION

SNEHASIS MONDAL*

Vidyasagar College, Kolkata, India

Abstract: This paper elaborates on the determinants of poverty disparity between STs (Scheduled Tribes) and non-STs. STs are the most deprived social group in rural India. It is argued that the alienation of the ST people from their land and territorial resources contributes to their deprivation. However, empirical evidence on the role of land dispossession, irrigation, changes in occupation structure, etc., on poverty disparities between STs and non-STs is still limited. Using a state-level panel data set from rural India from 1983 to 2017-18, this study tries to capture the effect of land dispossession, irrigation and occupation structure changes on poverty disparities between ST and non-ST communities. This study reveals that poverty disparities between ST and non-ST/SC (SC stands for Scheduled Castes) rose because of occupational choices and disparities in land and education between ST and non-SC/ST.

Keywords: Poverty disparity, Scheduled Tribe, Agrarian distress, Displacement, State-level data, Panel regression, Indian social groups

1. Introduction

India has experienced neoliberal reforms associated with liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation since the early 1990s. Since the reform was initiated, ST areas have experienced significant social unrest and protests. Gandhian economic development model, which prioritises the self-development of the rural regions, had never been discussed in India either by the mainstream economists or its left-wing critics (Chakravarty, 1987). The development path initiated by Indian policymakers has not differed significantly from that of the Western economies, where a commodity-centred approach has been prioritised. The higher value of capital per worker has always been considered essential for improving the standard of living. The construction of dams for irrigation and power generation, and different industrial projects financed by the government, were established predominantly in the

*Correspondence to: Snehasis Mondal, Assistant Professor, Vidyasagar College, Kolkata 700 006, India. Email: snehasis.research@gmail.com